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THE ROLE OF SOCIALLY-ORIENTED ENTERPRISES IN UKRAINE'S ECONOMY DURING MARTIAL LAW

РОЛЬ СОЦІАЛЬНО-ОРІЄНТОВАНОГО ПІДПРИЄМСТВА В ЕКОНОМІЦІ УКРАЇНИ В УМОВАХ ВОЄННОГО СТАНУ

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Філіппов В.Ю., Нейков С.О., Мороз О.М. Роль соціально-орієнтованого підприємства в економіці України в умовах воєнного стану. Науково-методична стаття.

У статті досліджується роль соціально орієнтованих підприємств в економіці України в умовах воєнного стану. Висвітлюються ключові аспекти їх діяльності, зокрема вплив на соціальну стабільність, підтримку постраждалих громад, забезпечення робочих місць для вразливих груп населення та відновлення місцевої економіки. Автори аналізують основні виклики, з якими стикаються соціальні підприємства під час війни, включаючи проблеми фінансування, законодавчої невизначеності та безпеки. Важливу увагу приділено ролі міжнародних та державних організацій у підтримці таких підприємств. У дослідженні окреслюються перспективи подальшого розвитку соціального підприємництва в Україні, а також можливості його масштабування та підвищення впливу на вирішення соціальних проблем. У статті також зазначено, що, незважаючи на існуючі виклики, соціальні підприємства демонструють високу гнучкість та здатність адаптуватися до нових умов. Як висновок, стаття пропонує рекомендації щодо вдосконалення механізмів фінансової підтримки, розробки чіткої законодавчої бази для регулювання діяльності соціально орієнтованих підприємств та створення стратегій для підвищення їхньої ефективності та впливу на суспільство.

Ключові слова: соціально орієнтоване підприємництво, воєнний стан, економічна стійкість, соціальна стабільність, підтримка громад, відновлення економіки, фінансування, законодавче регулювання

Filippov V.Yu., Neykov S.O., Moroz O.M. The Role of Socially-Oriented Enterprises in Ukraine's Economy During Martial Law. Scientific and methodical article.

This article explores the role of socially-oriented enterprises in Ukraine's economy during martial law. It highlights key aspects of their activities, including their impact on social stability, support for affected communities, job creation for vulnerable groups, and the recovery of local economies. The authors analyze the main challenges faced by social enterprises during the war, including issues of funding, legal uncertainty, and security. Special attention is given to the role of international and governmental organizations in supporting such enterprises. The study outlines the prospects for the further development of social entrepreneurship in Ukraine, as well as opportunities for scaling and increasing its impact on solving social problems. The article also notes that, despite the existing challenges, social enterprises demonstrate a high degree of flexibility and the ability to adapt to new conditions. In conclusion, the article offers recommendations for improving financial support mechanisms, developing a clear legislative framework to regulate the activities of socially-oriented enterprises, and creating strategies to enhance their effectiveness and societal impact.

Keywords: socially-oriented entrepreneurship, martial law, economic resilience, social stability, community support, economic recovery, funding, legislative regulation

Socially-oriented entrepreneurship plays a crucial role in ensuring economic resilience and social integration, especially in the face of current challenges posed by martial law in Ukraine. Russian aggression has led to significant destruction of infrastructure, an increase in internally displaced persons, rising unemployment, and widespread poverty. At the same time, new social problems are emerging that require immediate responses from both the state and the private sector. Socially-oriented enterprises, which combine economic activity with solving social and environmental issues, have gained even greater significance in these circumstances.

On the one hand, these enterprises have the opportunity to respond promptly to social challenges by providing support to affected communities, creating jobs for vulnerable groups, and contributing to the recovery

of local economies. On the other hand, they face numerous difficulties, including a lack of funding, disruption of supply chains, security issues, and overall economic instability. In the context of military conflict, traditional business models become less effective, requiring socially-oriented enterprises to adapt to new conditions, apply innovative approaches, and engage in close cooperation with the government, international organizations, and local communities.

Thus, there is an urgent need to study the problems faced by socially-oriented enterprises under martial law, develop strategies for their support, and create effective models for their functioning during a crisis. This research is particularly relevant in the context of Ukraine's post-war economic recovery and the integration of socially responsible businesses into the national development strategy.

Analysis of recent researches and publications

Socially-oriented entrepreneurship is an approach to business that focuses not only on generating profit but also on addressing important social or environmental issues. This business model combines commercial and social goals, directing part of its income towards supporting social initiatives or solving public problems [1].

The theoretical foundation of the research is based on the works of leading foreign and domestic scholars dedicated to studying the formation of socially-oriented entrepreneurship business models. In the process of writing this article, the works of prominent scholars such as Orel Yu. [1], Bohatyr N. [2], Holubiak N. [3], Kornetskyi A. [4], Kyfiak V., Malysh L. [5], Kosovych B. [6], Melnyk O. [7], Svynchuk A., Kornetskyi A., Honcharova M., Nazaryk V., Husak N., Tumanova A. [8], and Sotula O. V. [9], among many others, were studied.

The main laws regulating entrepreneurial activity in Ukraine include:

- The Economic Code of Ukraine;
- The Civil Code of Ukraine;
- The Law of Ukraine "On Entrepreneurship".

The main principles of socially-oriented entrepreneurship include the combination of entrepreneurial activities with a focus on social goals and the creation of innovative approaches to solving social problems. Such enterprises may collaborate with various stakeholders, including business structures, governmental bodies, charitable foundations, non-profit organizations, and other economic entities [10].

Unsolved aspects of the problem

Despite the growing role of socially-oriented enterprises during martial law, several unresolved aspects require further research and solutions.

First, the issue of effective financial support for social enterprises remains relevant. Due to the unstable economic situation and limited resources, many enterprises face difficulties in attracting the necessary funds to continue their activities and implement social projects. Although international grants and support programs exist, the mechanisms for accessing them need improvement.

Second, there is the issue of the lack of a clear legislative framework to regulate the activities of socially-oriented enterprises in Ukraine. Legislative initiatives to support such enterprises are underdeveloped, creating legal uncertainty and limiting their potential for growth. A deeper exploration of legislative initiatives that would foster the sustainable development of social enterprises in crisis conditions is required.

Third, security challenges and the organization of social enterprises' work under martial law remain unresolved. The lack of a stable security situation in many regions of Ukraine complicates the activities of social enterprises, especially those involved in humanitarian aid and supporting internally displaced persons. The issue of protecting social entrepreneurs, their property, and their clients needs further study.

In addition, the question of scaling social enterprises and their impact on addressing social problems remains unresolved. Strategies need to be developed that allow socially-oriented enterprises to expand their societal influence, particularly by leveraging innovation and new technologies.

To ensure the effective operation of socially-oriented enterprises in wartime, it is necessary to address issues related to financial support, improving the legislative framework, ensuring security, and expanding the scale of their activities.

The main part

Before the full-scale invasion, socially-oriented enterprises in Ukraine already played a significant role in addressing various social issues. They operated in areas such as healthcare, education, support for low-income populations, environmental protection, and human rights. Social enterprises developed with the support of local communities, government programs, and international organizations, contributing to job creation, improving quality of life, and promoting social integration for vulnerable groups.

Social activities before the invasion were characterized by relative stability and predictability, allowing enterprises to effectively plan and implement their programs. Governments and donor organizations actively supported social initiatives through grants, subsidies, and other forms of funding. Many social enterprises had the opportunity to establish long-term partnerships and develop sustainable development strategies. Socially-oriented entrepreneurship occupies an important niche in the country's economy, especially during martial law [11]. During the war, such enterprises play a key role in maintaining social stability by addressing pressing social issues and contributing to the recovery of economic activity in affected areas. They provide necessary

assistance to impacted communities, create jobs, ensure access to healthcare and educational services, and support veterans and their families. The general directions of social assistance before the war are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. General directions of social assistance before February 24, 2022

Sector	Assistance Areas
Healthcare	– Support for low-income groups in accessing medical services
	– Implementation of disease prevention and treatment programs
	– Provision of psychological support and counseling
Education	– Access to education for children from low-income families
	– Support for educational programs for children with special needs
	– Scholarships and grants for talented students
Support for Low-Income	– Social payments and assistance for low-income families
	– Programs for social adaptation and integration
	– Distribution of food packages and essential goods
Human Rights and Justice	– Protection of the rights of children, women, and the elderly
	– Combating discrimination and domestic violence
	– Support for social equality and justice programs
Ecology and Sustainability	– Implementation of environmental projects to preserve the environment
	– Support for renewable energy development initiatives
	– Educational programs on environmental awareness
Social Inclusion	– Programs supporting people with disabilities
	– Ensuring infrastructure accessibility for people with limited mobility
	– Integration of vulnerable groups into society
Unemployment Support	– Training programs and workshops for the unemployed
	– Microcrediting and grants for small business development
	– Consultations and support for starting a business
Cultural Development	– Support for cultural initiatives and events
	– Leisure programs for children and youth from low-income families
	– Arts and creativity development programs
Humanitarian Aid	– Assistance to victims of natural disasters and emergencies
	– Refugee and internally displaced persons (IDP) support programs
	– Meeting basic needs of people in crisis situations

Source: authors' own elaboration

The directions of social assistance in Ukraine before February 24, 2022, and after the start of the full-scale invasion, including the challenges faced by social enterprises and key partners in providing assistance, are illustrated in Figure 1.

The diagram presented in Figure 1 provides a detailed overview of the changes in the directions of social assistance in Ukraine before and after the full-scale invasion. Before February 24, 2022, social assistance focused on various aspects, such as healthcare, education, support for low-income groups, human rights, environmental protection, social inclusion, gender equality, support for the unemployed, business development, sustainable development, and cultural advancement [12]. These areas covered a wide range of social needs and contributed to improving the quality of life for the population.

After the full-scale invasion, the priorities of social assistance shifted significantly. The main challenges faced by socially-oriented enterprises and other organizations included financial difficulties, logistical issues, safety concerns, population displacement, and lack of electricity and communication. During wartime, these challenges demand new approaches and quick adaptation.

Social assistance began to focus on immediate aid provided by both the government and international partners, as well as on establishing new partnerships with organizations such as the UN, IOM, RED CROSS, USAID, CARITAS INTERNATIONALIS, UNICEF, and others. Assistance efforts were redirected toward innovative approaches, including the use of new technologies and remote work, as well as social integration programs for veterans and internally displaced persons (IDPs).

After February 24, 2022, social assistance focused on stabilization and rehabilitation support. Stabilization aid includes financial and humanitarian assistance, shelter organization, support for winter adaptation, repairs after shelling, and aid for IDPs and veterans. Rehabilitation support covers business relocation and recovery, retraining and education, employment restoration, and the development of new businesses [13].

The diagram highlights the importance of partnerships with international and local organizations for the effective implementation of social programs during martial law. It also demonstrates the need to adapt social initiatives to new challenges, ensuring support for the most vulnerable populations and contributing to the restoration of the country's socio-economic stability.

Figure 1. Directions of social assistance in Ukraine before and after the full-scale invasion
 Source: compiled by authors on materials [10, 11, 14]

In times of war, when traditional businesses face significant challenges, social enterprises demonstrate flexibility and the ability to adapt to new circumstances. They actively engage local resources and collaborate with public organizations and government bodies to efficiently distribute aid and implement social programs. Moreover, such enterprises can quickly respond to changing local needs, providing timely support and assistance [26].

Social entrepreneurship plays a crucial role during martial law, helping address many social problems and maintaining economic stability. Its significance becomes particularly evident during crisis periods, when rapid adaptation to new conditions and effective use of limited resources are required.

The primary role of social entrepreneurship is to combine business models with a social mission. This enables addressing urgent social problems through innovative and sustainable approaches. Social enterprises create jobs, provide educational and healthcare services, support veterans and IDPs, and promote environmental sustainability [14].

During the war, social enterprises demonstrate high flexibility and the ability to quickly adapt to changes. They actively collaborate with the government, international organizations, and other stakeholders to effectively implement social programs. These enterprises can swiftly respond to the needs of local communities, providing humanitarian aid, supporting refugees, and restoring infrastructure.

Social entrepreneurship also contributes to economic development by creating new opportunities for entrepreneurial activities among vulnerable groups. This helps reduce inequality and promotes social integration. In addition, social enterprises can mitigate social and economic risks, contributing to the overall economic resilience of the country. Social entrepreneurship is a critical tool for supporting society and the economy during wartime, providing necessary aid to affected communities, contributing to economic recovery, and strengthening social stability.

The main measures distinguishing social entrepreneurship from traditional business before the full-scale invasion are outlined in Table 2.

Table 2. Differences between social entrepreneurship and traditional business before February 24, 2022

Criterion	Social Entrepreneurship	Traditional Entrepreneurship
Goal	Addressing social or environmental issues, creating positive social impact	Maximizing profit for owners or shareholders
Profit Distribution	Reinvesting part or all profits into social projects and initiatives	Distributing profits among owners or shareholders
Core Activities	Providing products and services that have social or environmental value	Providing products and services to generate profit
Funding	May receive grants, donor aid, social investments	Primary funding through product and service sales, investments from private individuals and institutions
Community Engagement	Close collaboration with local communities, active involvement in social projects	Community engagement is limited to marketing and corporate social responsibility
Management	Considers social metrics alongside financial ones, employs ethical management approaches	Focuses primarily on financial performance and business process efficiency
Sustainability	Focused on long-term social and environmental sustainability	Focused on long-term financial stability
Target Audience	Vulnerable populations, communities in need of support	General consumer population
Innovation	Uses innovation to solve social problems and improve social initiative effectiveness	Uses innovation to increase profitability and competitiveness
Marketing	Emphasizes social and environmental benefits of products or services	Emphasizes benefits of products or services for consumers

Source: authors' own elaboration

This table illustrates the key differences between social entrepreneurship and traditional entrepreneurship before the war, highlighting the social orientation, funding methods, management approaches, and community interaction in social enterprises.

The main measures distinguishing social entrepreneurship from traditional business after the start of the war are outlined in Table 3.

Table 3. Differences between social entrepreneurship and traditional business after February 24, 2022

Criterion	Social Entrepreneurship	Traditional Entrepreneurship
Goal	Addressing urgent social problems, supporting affected communities, contributing to economic recovery	Stabilization efforts aimed at profit maximization, supporting the Armed Forces of Ukraine, volunteer activities, donations, and fundraising for military support
Profit Distribution	Reinvesting profits into humanitarian projects, refugee and veteran support	Profit distribution while allocating contributions for the needs of the Armed Forces, charitable donations, and supporting volunteer organizations
Core Activities	Providing products and services focused on assisting war-affected communities and supporting local populations	Producing goods/services to generate profit, contributing part of the production to the military or providing services that support military personnel
Funding	Receiving grants, donor aid, social investments, and support from international organizations	Primary funding through product and service sales, investments from private individuals and institutions
Community Engagement	Active collaboration with local and international organizations, involving communities in recovery processes	Volunteer initiatives, joint projects with public organizations to support the state and military, increasing corporate social responsibility
Management	Considers social indicators alongside financial ones, ethical management approaches, adapting to wartime conditions	Focus primarily on financial metrics and business process efficiency, coordination with volunteer and charitable organizations for fundraising to support Ukraine's defense forces
Sustainability	Focus on social, economic, and environmental sustainability during crisis	Participation in various grant and government support programs for business
Target Audience	Vulnerable populations, war-affected communities, veterans, internally displaced persons (IDPs)	General and basic needs of the population, military needs
Innovation	Using innovation to address social problems rapidly, remote work	Seeking innovations to improve products for the military, organize volunteer activities, and enhance profitability
Marketing	Emphasizes social and environmental benefits of products or services, supports humanitarian initiatives	Showcasing fundraising results, supporting military and volunteer initiatives in communications and marketing

Source: authors' own elaboration

This table illustrates the key differences between social entrepreneurship and traditional entrepreneurship after the war began, highlighting changes in goals, funding methods, management, and community interaction that have occurred in the context of the conflict.

Additionally, socially-oriented enterprises contribute to economic development by creating new opportunities for entrepreneurial activity among vulnerable groups. They promote social integration and reduce inequality, which is especially important during times of crisis. Through their activities, these enterprises help mitigate social and economic risks, contributing to the overall economic resilience of the country. Socially-oriented entrepreneurship is an essential element of the modern economy, fostering the creation of long-term social and environmental solutions. Its impact is evident in several aspects of economic development.

These enterprises open up new markets and opportunities for economic growth by offering innovative products and services aimed at solving social problems. They attract consumers who value social responsibility and sustainability, which helps create new markets and jobs, stimulating overall economic development.

Social enterprises also increase productivity and competitiveness. By combining a social mission with business models, they promote efficient management and innovative approaches to doing business. This enhances productivity and the competitiveness of the economy as a whole.

Such enterprises play a crucial role in supporting entrepreneurship among vulnerable populations. By providing support and opportunities for self-realization, they promote social integration and reduce inequality.

Addressing social issues and promoting environmental sustainability strengthens economic resilience. Socially-oriented enterprises help reduce social and environmental risks that affect the overall stability of the economy. In the context of war, caused by Russian aggression, they play a key role in assisting affected communities and restoring the economy in liberated territories. The war leads to the destruction of infrastructure, an increase in internally displaced persons, and other social problems that require immediate attention.

Social enterprises can become an essential resource for supporting affected communities by providing necessary services and creating jobs for local residents. They play a critical role in economic recovery, offering educational and medical services, and supporting veterans and their families.

For social enterprises to succeed in a war zone, support from the state, international organizations, and public structures is essential. This support can include financial aid, management consultations, and protection from risks associated with the unstable political and economic situation.

An example of successful social entrepreneurship during the war is the Ukrainian organization "Ukrainian Frontiers". This social enterprise was created to support ATO veterans and their families, providing them with jobs in production workshops and offering social services such as medical care, psychological support, and professional development assistance.

The success of "Ukrainian Frontiers" is not only measured by financial indicators but also by its impact on the quality of life of those affected and its contribution to social stability in liberated areas. The approach to social entrepreneurship during wartime must take into account the specific needs and challenges of the affected regions.

This may include developing specialized support programs, access to financing, training for communities and businesses on social entrepreneurship, and creating networks and exchanges of experience between different social enterprises.

Social entrepreneurship during wartime requires special attention to security issues. Frequent instances of violence or interference from armed groups may pose a danger to social entrepreneurs and their clients. Therefore, it is crucial to establish protective mechanisms and evacuation plans to prevent potential risks.

After the full-scale invasion, social activities in Ukraine underwent significant changes due to the sharp deterioration in the security situation and economic instability. The war has led to infrastructure destruction, a significant increase in internally displaced persons, rising unemployment, and widespread poverty. Under these conditions, socially-oriented enterprises have faced new challenges but also gained new opportunities for impact.

Partnerships with local authorities and local public organizations are also crucial for the successful functioning of social enterprises. This can include joint development programs, resource-sharing, and collective advocacy for creating a favorable environment for social entrepreneurs.

The business environment during the war can be extremely challenging due to the uncertainty of the political and economic situation, which creates risks for businesses. Therefore, social enterprises must be prepared for rapid changes in strategy and business plans, as well as reliable mechanisms for monitoring and risk assessment.

Successful social entrepreneurship during wartime requires actively involving the local population and creating conditions for their participation in decision-making and program development. This will ensure that social enterprises respond to the real needs and priorities of local communities.

Socially-oriented enterprises play a critically important role in Ukraine's economy during martial law. They not only continue their primary mission of solving social and environmental problems but also adapt to the new challenges brought about by the war. Due to their ability to respond quickly to the needs of local communities, they provide essential humanitarian assistance, support internally displaced persons, veterans, and other vulnerable groups.

Socially-oriented enterprises actively attract international grants, donor funds, and investments, allowing them to continue their activities even in difficult conditions. They collaborate with the government, international organizations, and public structures, creating effective partnerships for implementing social programs.

In times of war, these enterprises demonstrate high flexibility and innovation, using new technologies and approaches to support economic resilience and social integration. They play a key role in restoring damaged infrastructure, creating jobs, and ensuring social stability.

Moreover, it is worth noting that even non-socially-oriented businesses during the war actively participate in donations, fundraising, and other volunteer activities. They support the Armed Forces of Ukraine, help meet humanitarian needs, organize the production of goods for the front, and cooperate with volunteer organizations. This demonstrates the high level of social responsibility of businesses in general, contributing to the overall economic and social recovery of the country.

Thus, socially-oriented enterprises are indispensable participants in the economic and social recovery of the country. Their activities help reduce social and economic risks, strengthen economic resilience, and support the population during the war. The involvement of traditional businesses in volunteer activities further amplifies this positive impact, uniting efforts to achieve a common goal-victory and the recovery of Ukraine.

Socially-oriented entrepreneurship during the war can play a critical role in the recovery of affected territories and provide support to those impacted by the conflict. However, for it to function successfully, comprehensive support from the state, international, and public organizations is needed, along with the development of special approaches and strategies that take into account the specifics of war conditions. Socially-oriented entrepreneurship fosters the creation of new markets, increases productivity, develops entrepreneurship among vulnerable groups, and strengthens economic resilience during wartime.

Conclusions

In conclusion, socially-oriented enterprises have become vital contributors to Ukraine's economic and social resilience during martial law. Their ability to quickly adapt to the wartime challenges has allowed them to play a key role in providing essential services to vulnerable groups, including internally displaced persons, veterans, and affected communities. These enterprises have shown great flexibility and innovation in addressing both social and economic issues while actively contributing to the restoration of the country's infrastructure and the promotion of social stability.

Their work, supported by international grants, government collaboration, and local community involvement, demonstrates how socially responsible business models can create lasting social and environmental impact, even in times of extreme crisis. Furthermore, the active engagement of traditional businesses in volunteer activities, donations, and support for the Armed Forces of Ukraine highlights the broader shift toward a socially conscious business culture that strengthens the country's overall recovery efforts.

For socially-oriented entrepreneurship to continue thriving and contributing to Ukraine's recovery, ongoing support from the state, international organizations, and civil society will be crucial. This includes financial aid, security measures, and strategic planning tailored to the unique demands of wartime. With the right support and partnerships, socially-oriented enterprises will not only help rebuild the economy but also foster a more inclusive, resilient, and sustainable society in Ukraine.

In the face of adversity, socially-oriented businesses prove that the combination of economic activity and social responsibility can drive meaningful change, supporting Ukraine's long-term recovery and stability in the most challenging circumstances.

The prospects for further research in the field of socially-oriented entrepreneurship during martial law include the development of sustainable models for such enterprises, an assessment of their impact on solving social problems and economic resilience, the study of effective financial support mechanisms, as well as the role of innovations and technologies in improving their efficiency. An important direction is the examination of cooperation between social enterprises and traditional businesses, as well as legislative and governmental support mechanisms that foster their development in times of crisis.

Abstract

The article analyzes the current state of the system of public management of the development of tourism and recreation potential of Ukraine. Key aspects of the functioning of public administration in this area are considered, including the legal framework, organizational structure and mechanisms of interaction between state bodies and the private sector. The effectiveness of existing approaches to the management of tourist and recreational resources was evaluated and the main problems that prevent their optimal use were identified. Based on the obtained results, recommendations are proposed for improving the management system aimed at increasing the competitiveness of Ukraine in the international tourist market and ensuring the sustainable development of its recreational areas.

The analysis of the state of the system of public management of the development of tourism and recreation potential of Ukraine showed that the existing system needs significant improvement. Despite the existence of a legal framework and certain organizational structures, the effectiveness of management of tourist and recreational resources remains insufficient. The main problems are the fragmentation of management functions, insufficient coordination between public authorities and the private sector, as well as limited use of modern technologies and innovative approaches.

To improve the situation, it is necessary to implement integrated approaches to management, which involve close cooperation between all interested parties, improve the regulatory and legal framework, and actively use marketing and digital tools. This will make it possible to increase the efficiency of the use of tourist and recreational resources, increase the attractiveness of Ukraine as a tourist destination at the international level, and contribute to the sustainable development of the regions.

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